

TABLE I—ANALYSIS OF FERRO-CHROME ORES AND ALLOYS

Sl. No.	Sample with composition	Metal analysed	Amount taken (mg)	Amount recovered (mg)	% of Standard recovery	Deviation very
1.	Synthetic mixture Fe(III):Cr(VI)~1:10 Cr	Fe	4.74	4.72	99.56	0.04
		Cr	43.38	43.61	100.60	0.3
2.	Synthetic mixture Fe(III):Cr(VI)~10:1 Cr	Fe	47.26	46.96	99.40	0.25
		Cr	5.06	5.09	100.60	0.03
3.	Synthetic ferro-chrome alloy Fe(III)-6%, Cr(VI)-72%	Fe	6.33	6.34	100.15	0.02
		Cr	12.70	12.78	100.70	0.05
4.	Extra low-carbon ferro-chrome alloy (Lot No. 1627 A) Fe-26.88%, Cr-72.53%	Fe	5.24	5.29	100.98	0.04
		Cr	12.33	12.16	98.60	0.20
5.	Stainless steel (69a) Cr-18.4% Ni-8.2%	Fe	35.60	34.73	97.60	0.80
		Cr	9.34	9.45	101.2	0.13
		Ni	3.67	3.69	100.60	0.01
6.	DSP alloy steel (A) Cr-23.75% Ni-20.41%	Fe	20.32	20.32	100.00	0.01
		Cr	9.52	9.41	98.86	0.12
		Ni	8.25	8.12	98.42	0.15
7.	Chrome-iron ore(49f) Cr ₂ O ₃ -43.1% FeO 15.3%	Fe	1.60	1.59	99.40	0.01
		Cr	3.94	3.95	100.20	0.01
8.*	Chrome-iron ore (49f)	Cr	10 μg	9.9 μg	99.00	0.08

* Exchanger taken -1.5g, column length (1.2 × 1.3) cm, Eluant volume -15 ml.

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References

1. N. J. SINGH and S. N. TANDON, *Talanta*, 1977, **24**, 459.
2. A. K. DE and A. K. SEN, *Talanta*, 1966, **13**, 1313.
3. F. Z. FROHLICH, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1959, **170**, 383.
4. K. ISAGAI and N. TAKESHITA, *Japan Analyst*, 1955, **4**, 222; *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, **50**, 11173 b.
5. D. A. SHISKOV, *Khin. Ind.* (Sofia), 1959, **31**, 113.
6. A. K. SEN and R. K. GHATUARY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 196.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, London, 3rd Edn., 1962.
8. A. K. SEN and R. K. GHATUARY, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1979, **295**, 414.
9. E. B. SANDELL, *Colorimetric estimation of traces of metals*, Interscience, N. Y., 3rd Edn., 1965.

Thermolysis of Substituted Ortho-Hydroxy Acetophenone Oxime Complexes with Bivalent Metals-Part II

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ROLE of ortho-hydroxy keto oximes in the last one decade has encouraged the chemists due to their inevitable application¹⁻⁵ in various fields. The ineffable efficiency of these compounds is due to the presence of phenolic group in vicinity of keto oxime group to act as bidentate ligands with bivalent metal ions for the formation of six membered ring of stable chelates. This manuscript records the vivid TGA interpretation of palladium, nickel and copper complexes with 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro acetophenone oxime, 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone oxime and 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone oxime.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligands :

The 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro acetophenone oxime (HMCAOX) ; m.p. 146°, 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone oxime (HCAOX) ; m.p. 181° and 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone oxime (HBAOX) ; m.p. 169-170° were prepared as early reported⁶.

The metal solutions were prepared by dissolving AnalaR grade metal chloride or sulphates in double-distilled water. The solutions of ligands were made in ethanol.

A Stanton thermobalance, model HT-SM range ambient 1600° with an accuracy of 1 mg was used for recording TGA at a heating rate of 5° per minute.

Preparation of complexes :

The complexes of palladium, nickel and copper were prepared by usual gravimetric method⁷ at pH 0.6 to 0.9, 5.5 to 8 and 3.0 to 4.5 respectively employing the solution of aforesaid oximes. These complexes are non-electrolytic in nature and are soluble in common non-polar solvents.

Results and Discussion

Thermolysis of Pd(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes with HBAOX : It is obvious from

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thermolysis curves (Fig. 1) that no loss in weight observed when all the complexes viz., Pd-HBAOX,

Ni-HBAOX and Cu-HBAOX are heated up to 140° which is an indication that the chelates are non-hydrated in nature. The order of thermal stability was found as Cu-HBAOX (200°) > Pd-HBAOX (180°) > Ni-HBAOX (160°). In the complexes of Pd(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) a rapid decomposition at 300°, 340° and 260° held with a weight loss of 39.0%, 55.0% and 49.5% respectively accompanied with a odour of disintegration products persists for days and furthermore the vapours are toxic when inhaled. The oxide formation is shown at 680° in nickel and 720° in copper complexes but in case of Pd-HBAOX the metal palladium is left at 640°. The thermal stability 200° of Cu-HBAOX is higher than Cu-salicylaldoxime, i.e., 140°.

It is evident from above thermogravimetric analysis that these chelates are as stable as chelates of resacetophenone oxime⁸ but more stable than those of nioxime⁹ and salicylaldoxime⁴.

Therefore, it is concluded that 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone oxime (HBAOX) is a better thermogravimetric reagent for Pd(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) than dimethylglyoxime, salicylaldoxime, nioxime and resacetophenone oxime, etc.

Thermolysis of Ni-HCAOX complex :

In view of the fate of this complex when subjected to the action of heat, a perfectly horizontal stretch is obtained up to 160° corresponds to the anhydrous $Ni(C_8H_7O_2NCl)_2$; this is well suited for the determination of nickel with an analytical factor (metal/metal-complex), i.e., 0.1746. A small weight loss in the temperature range 160-340° indicates the slow process of ignition of carbon. Beyond the temperature 340°, there is an abrupt weight loss of about 48.75% with a smoke and tenacious odour of disinfective product upto 360°, followed by a gradual loss in weight of 30.83% between 360-500°. After this temperature the organic matter disappeared and the final product is NiO at about 600° (Fig. 2).

Thermolysis of Cu(II)-HMCAOX complex :

The stability of this complex upto 200°, reveals its anhydrous nature. There is very little loss upto 300° (Fig. 2) but above this temperature, the vigorous decomposition commences accompanied by a weight loss of 47.89% upto 320° with a choking odour. In the region 320-620° the gradual weight loss takes place due to the process of pyrolysis and the thermograms runs smoothly. Finally, at 640° the CuO is obtained.

All the thermolysis data are tabulated in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—PYROLYSIS DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Thermal stability Temp. (°C)	Decomposition Temp. (°C)	Approximate Temp. (°C) of residue formation	Possible residue	Residue%	
						Calcd.	Found
Pd-HBAOX	Yellow	180	300	640	Palladium metal	18.89	17.67
Ni-HBAOX	Green	160	340	680	NiO	14.95	13.57
Cu-HBAOX	Buff	200	260	720	CuO	15.25	15.98
Ni-HCAOX	Green	160	340	600	NiO	17.46	17.08
Cu-HMCAOX	Buff	200	300	640	CuO	17.27	16.76

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References

1. S. N. PODDAR, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, **26**, 153; 1964, **27**, 67.
2. D. B. INGLE and D. D. KHANOLKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 609 and 103.
3. M. DESAI, B. M. DESAI, B. S. PATWARI and M. H. GANDHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 369.
4. U. K. RATHI, Ph.D. Thesis, Agra University, Agra.
5. Y. K. REDDY, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1965, **7A**, 368.
6. N. A. RAJU and K. NEELKANTAM, *Curr. Sci.* 1950, **19**, 383.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, 3rd Ed., 1968.
8. V. SESHAGIRI and S. BRAHAMJI, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1972, **262**, 275.
9. G. LIPTAY, E. M. PAPP and K. BURGERS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **34**, 247.
10. C. DUVAL, "Inorganic Thermogravimetric Analysis", Elsevier London, 1953, pp. 236, 259 and 347.

Chalcones XXIV : Studies on Chalcone Complexes of Fe(III) and Cr(III)

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THE chalcones and their analogues are well known as multiprotecting agents +1-3. The field of coordination chemistry of these compounds has not been investigated widely⁴. However, 2-hydroxy chalcones are found⁵⁻⁷ useful as gravimetric reagents for various cations. It is, therefore, thought worthwhile to undertake the synthesis, isolation and study of a few 3-d transition metal cation complexes, i.e., Fe(III) and Cr(III) with 8-hydroxy-5-quinolinyl chalcone. The complexes were prepared at an ionic strength of 0.005 mole in 90% aqueous methanol at boiling water temperature. The spectrophotometric and conductometric studies evaluated the stoichiometry of the complexes. The molecular conductance measurements were made

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with a view to study their stereochemistry. The characterisation of the complexes was done by elemental analysis. The I.R. spectra of the ligand 8-hydroxy-5-quinolinyl chalcone explores the possibility of chelation at $-OH$, $>C=O$ and $-C\equiv N$ groups.

Experimental

The solutions of metal nitrate of required strength were prepared in 90% aqueous methanol (v/v) of A.R. grade. The ligand 8-hydroxy-5-quinolinyl chalcone was obtained as reported⁷ and purified by repeated crystallisations and its homogeneity was checked by T.L.C. Spectrophotometric studies were made by Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20. Conductometric measurements were made with Toshniwal's conductivity bridge.

I.R. spectra was recorded in mujolmull with Beckmann spectrophotometer to study various important bands and the Gouy balance was used for the magnetic measurements. On the basis of spectrophotometric and conductometric results the stoichiometry of the complexes were found to be 1 : 3 metal ligand system. Double distilled water over alkaline potassium permanganate was used throughout the investigation and all the measurements were made at room temperature.

Isolation of the complexes :

The complexes were isolated by adding ligand solution to a hot methanolic solution of metal nitrates in the stoichiometric ratio of 3 : 1. The resulting dark coloured mixture was kept at about 50-60° over water bath with reflux condensor for about three hours, cooled filtered and the complex washed several times with cold absolute ethanol and finally recrystallised from dioxane.

Analysis :

Elemental analysis was performed by C.D.R.I., Lucknow and the metal components were determined gravimetrically⁸. The results are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric titration gave the stoichiometric ratio of the ligand to metal as 3 : 1. The molar composition of the complexes were further determined by mole-ratio method and confirmed by their elemental analysis.

The magnetic measurements of Fe(III) and Cr(III) complexes were carried out at 303°K by Gouy method and the μ_{eff} values were found to be 1.37 and 1.01 BM respectively indicates the formation of high ligand field, low spin octahedral